

PROCESSING TECHNIQUES OF CERAMIC PRODUCTS FOUND AT THE MONUMENT "UCHTEPA-BULOQMOZOR"

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Annotation: In this article, field research conducted at the Uchtepa Archaeological Complex in the Naryn district of Namangan Province has uncovered raw materials belonging to various types of handicrafts, the most common of which are ceramics. The material sources found during the field research, ie pottery, testify to the fact that the Uchtepa-2 monument lasted for three periods: the first antiquity, the last antiquity and the first Middle Ages.

Keywords: "Uchtepa-bulakmozor", pottery, quartz, pottery wheel, red angob, pottery.

The role of archeological sites in the study of the ancient history of our people is invaluable. Taking this into account, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "In order to improve the system of reliable protection and rational use of cultural heritage sites, it is necessary to adopt a program to support archaeological research and preservation of archaeological finds" [1: 318.].

In connection with the inclusion of Uchtepa village of Naryn district of Namangan region in the state program "Prosperous Village" in 2019, it became necessary to study the archeological monuments located in the village. Therefore, under the leadership of Academician Ahmadali Askarov, a project on "Uchtepa Bulakmozor archeological monuments and preparation for its transformation into a museum under the" Blue Sky "" was prepared for participation in the competition of the Ministry of Innovation Development for 2019-2020. The prepared scientific grant project won the competition. During the excavation of the Uchtepa 2 site in the past, several thousand pieces of pottery were found. They can be divided into two groups according to their processing techniques. The first type of pottery consists of a thick-walled pottery with a mixture of crushed quartz stone powder, a heavier, coarser, three-piece hand-made clay pottery. Some of them have darkened traces of fungus inside. The outer surface, especially the lower second half of the pot, was blackened by smoke. An oval handle is attached to the bottom of the pot.

Types of hand-made, non-polished pottery can include sawdust, water and grain, meat storage jars and jars. The ceramic complex of the facility is mostly composed of ceramic pottery. They were mainly pottery whisks, the flat bottom of pottery, and the fragments of various ceramic pottery that could not be repaired. Among them are dozens of bus pieces, as well as archeological pottery.

As mentioned above, the body wall of the bright red angob ceramics was very thin, and most of them were elegant ceramics made of pottery. These include overturned vases, bowls and palms, jugs and spherical bowls, plates and low-side bowls, bowls and cups with handles, long-legged ashtrays, etc. forms cult vessels. They are baked in a two-tiered jar. That is why the quality of their national equipment is high, the dishes are light, the products of ceramics are highly developed. These vessels were made without the addition of sand or quartz powder to the mud, but were carefully prepared on the soil, which was cleaned of water from the ground with water. That is why they are light, elegant and marketable. Most of the pottery of different quality dates back to the early antiquity. Among the fragments of pottery there are fragments of various pottery with dark angoba. Their body wall is thicker than that of ancient ceramics, and there are elements of roughness in their shape. These same vessels belong to the second stage of antiquity. The deterioration in the quality of pottery was probably due to the influence of Turkic-speaking nomadic herders who came to the land from the northeast of the Syrdarya. Yu. A. Zadneprovsky also wrote [9: 192.].

In fact, from the 3rd to the 2nd centuries BC, Turkic-speaking Hun tribes gradually began to enter this land. .

Application

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